

Bank Loan Prediction Using Machine Learning

Ayan Alam
B.Tech, IT (4th year)
ayanalam186@gmail.com

Manoj Kumar Chaurasiya
Assistant Professor
manoj.chaurasiya@imsec.ac.in

Divyansh Singh
B.Tech, IT (4th year)
divyansh8954singh@gmail.com

Harshit Sinha
B.Tech, IT (4th year)
harshit0551@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In our banking system, banks sell many products, but credit lines are the main source of income for any bank. So they can earn interest on these credited loans. A bank's profit or loss is highly dependent on its credit. That is, whether the customer will repay the loan or default on the payment. By predicting loan defaults, banks can reduce their bad assets. This makes the study/research of this system or phenomenon very important. Earlier research from this era has shown that there are numerous ways to study the problem of credit default management. However, making correct predictions is so important to maximizing profits that it is essential to study the properties of different methods and how they compare. A very important approach in predictive analytics is used to study the problem of predicting loan defaults: (i) data collection, (ii) data cleaning, and (iii) performance evaluation. Experimental tests show that his Naive Bayes model outperforms other models in terms of credit prediction.

KEYWORDS

Customer loan, Prediction, evaluation processing, classification models.

1 Introduction

Credit forecasts are very useful for both bank employees and applicants. The purpose of this document is to provide a quick, immediate and easy method for selecting suitable applicants. You will first apply for credit after your company or bank has verified your credit eligibility. A company or bank wants to automate the credit qualification process (in real time) based on customer details provided when filling out an application form. These details include gender, marital status, education, number of dependents, income, loan amount, and credit history. This project collected data of previous clients of different banks who were approved for loans with different parameters. Therefore, a machine learning model is trained on this dataset and gives accurate results. The main goal of this project is to predict loan security. Predict loan collateral using SVM and Naive Bayes algorithms. First, the data is cleaned to avoid missing values in the data set.

You can set deadlines to see if a candidate can approve a loan. Loan prediction technology licenses given to well-defined candidates are intended to very likely have the necessary assumptions in mind. The paper is a complete oversight of the banking/financial company's power, the entire forecasting process is done in secret, and no colleague has the ability to warn the process. Results for a particular credit ID can be shared with different parts of the business so that the application can process them accordingly. This system predicts whether a loan will be approved or rejected. Data Collection, Data Preprocessing (Data Cleaning), Model Selection, Model Evaluation, Model Classification, Results (Output).

2 Related Work

Machine learning also uses efficient and semi-automated data knowledge extraction to determine if a loan is approved [6][8]. Classification could be supervised learning where the answer is categorical, i.e. unit of range of values in a finite unordered set. Scikit Learn is used to simplify the classification problem. The main advantage of this system is that the company does not need to maintain a ground team to verify and verify customer records. Using this predictive model, you can easily check if a loan needs approval.

This contribution attempts to develop a flexible graphic concept for user interfaces connected via a browser interface. Our goal is to implement a machine learning model to classify Mastercard fraud with the highest possible accuracy from the data set collected by Kaggle. After initial knowledge exploration, we tend to find that we can implement a random forest model for the most faithful reporting.

Use Kaggle dataset for credit card fraud detection, pandas in dataframe with class==0 for no fraud and class==1 for fraud, matplotlib for plotting fraud and non-fraud data, I used train_test_split for data extraction (split array or matrix). for random training and testing subsets) and used logistic regression machine learning algorithms for fraud detection and pressure prediction scores according to the algorithm. Finally, the confusion matrix was plotted to true and predicted. The SVM was used to build and train the model, and the demo was prepared using human cell recordings to classify the cells according to whether the test was benign (mild condition) or dangerous (bad condition). The Support Vector Machine is a managed learning model that uses affiliation r-learning computation to analyze the attributes and salient design information used to

classify applications. An SVM can perform permutations by using a kernel tricks by explicitly mapping its input into a high-dimensional attribute space .

“Machine Learning Based Loan Approval Prediction” Author – Kumar Arun, Garg Ishan, Kaur Sanmeet Year –2018 The main purpose of this paper is to predict whether it is safe to allocate a loan to a particular person. This white paper is divided into four sections: (I) data collection (ii) comparison of machine learning models using the collected data (iii) training the system using the most promising models (iv) testing. “Exploring Machine Learning Algorithms to Predict the Loan Sanctions Process” Authors – E. Chandra Blessie, R. Rekha – Year – 2019 For a growing economy like India to function smoothly, credit should be given to businesses and individuals It is essential to provide With more and more customers applying for loans from banks and non-bank financial companies (NBFCs), a standard solution and safe process for lending money to borrowers for banks and his NBFCs with limited capital. has become a real challenge. their financial needs. Moreover, NBFC's inventory has recently plummeted significantly in terms of its share price. It has contributed to the contagion spreading to other financial stocks and has recently negatively impacted benchmarks. This paper attempts to summarize the risks involved

in choosing the right person to repay the loan on time, thereby putting the bank's non-performing assets (NPA) on hold. This is achieved by feeding a trained machine learning model with a customer's past record of purchasing a loan from the bank, resulting in accurate results. The main focus of this paper is to determine whether it is safe to assign loans to specific individuals. This document contains sections on (i) data collection, (ii) data cleansing, and (iii) performance evaluation. Experimental tests show that the Naive Bayes model performs better. Experimental tests show that his Naive Bayes model outperforms other models in terms of credit prediction.

“Loan Prediction Using Machine Learning Models” Year – 2019 Whether it is safe to assign loans to specific people. This document contains sections on (i) data collection, (ii) data cleansing, and (iii) performance evaluation. Empirical tests show that the Naive Bayes model outperforms other models on credit prediction.

3 Proposed Approach

This system predicts whether a loan will be approved or rejected by following steps/procedures:

- a. Data Collection
- b. Data Preprocessing (Data Cleaning)
- c. Model Selection
- d. Model Evaluation, Model Classification, Results (Output). Results/Output
- e. Results/Output

3.1 Loan Record

Loan records are very helpful in the system to predict more accurate results. Using loan records, the system automatically

predicts which customer loans to approve and which to reject. The system accepts the credit application form as input. A valid form of application must be provided as input for processing.

3.2 Determine training data and test data

Normally, the system divides the data set into training set and test set, and uses most of the data for training and some of the data for testing. After the system has been processed using the training set, predictions are made on the test set.

3.3 Data Cleansing and Processing

Data cleansing is when the system detects and corrects corrupted or inaccurate records from the database, identifies incomplete, inaccurate, inaccurate or irrelevant parts of the data and removes contamination. means to replace, modify, or detect or rough data. In data processing, the system transforms data from a particular format into a more usable and desirable format. H. Make them more meaningful and informative.

Figure 1: Framework of our proposed approach

In the framework of our proposed approach, we are giving some inputs to the system and the system determines the training data and then it starts data processing. After that we use two algorithms of machine learning namely:

- A. SVM (Support Vector Machine)
- B. Naïve bayes algorithm

After that the process gets evaluated and the most favourable output/result is used. So here we can confidently conclude that Naive Bayes is very efficient and gives better results than other models. It works

perfectly and meets all the banker's requirements. This system calculates results accurately and accurately. Predict with great accuracy whether a loan will be approved or rejected.

Figure 2: Comparison of accuracy and execution time

4 Experiments

In this experiment, we first collected the data, used (.description()) to understand the data, then analyzed the data, looking for missing/null/unsolicited data in the data set, creating a confusion matrix (accuracy, precision, recall, f1-score) and finally modeling, i H. methods, procedures used. The project/model is designed to detect errors in data at a lower level of detail. Data validation is built into the system in almost every area where users can make mistakes. The system will not accept invalid information. If invalid information is entered, the system will prompt the user like a shot and the user will have to re-enter the information. If the information is correct, the system accepts the information. Validation is included where necessary. This system is designed to be user-friendly. In other words, the system is designed

to interact effectively with the user. A system was developed with a pop-up menu.

Barplot(): A bar plot represents an estimate of central tendency for a numeric variable with the height of each rectangle and provides some indication of the uncertainty around that estimate using error bars.

```

sns.barplot(x=data_train['TotalIncome'],
            y=data_train['Loan_Status'],
            hue=data_train[' Education'])
  
```

4.1 Problem Statement

Finance agencies, banks are deals with different forms of loans along with schooling mortgage, keep loans, home loans, non-public loans and many others all are part of our us of a loan types. all the agencies and banks are found in villages, cities, towns. After patron practice for loan those banks/organizations want to validate the consumer information for that candidate eligible for loan or now not. the main cause of the machine is applicant loan accepted or no longer based on train fashions.Loans should not become limited to any financial institutions.

4.2 Proposed Model

In gadget learning, we are the use of semi-computerized extraction of knowledge of statistics for figuring out whether or not a loan would be permitted or no longer [6][8]. category will be a supervised learning inside which the reaction is categorical that's its values vicinity unit in finite unordered set. To easily the matter of type, scikit study are used. The praim primacy of this device is organisation want now not has to preserve a floor team to validate and verify the purchaser records. they could effortlessly take a look at whether or not the loan needs to be accepted or now not by using this prediction version.

On this paper we try to develop user interface flexibly pictures concepts in thoughts, related via a browser interface. Our aim

is to enforce device learning version so one can classify, to the first-rate capacity degree of accuracy, master card fraud from a dataset collected from Kaggle. as soon as preliminary knowledge exploration, we have a propensity to knew we'd put in force a random woodland version for satisfactory accuracy reports.

Random wooded area, because it became an excellent candidate for binary category. Python sklearn library changed into used to implement the project, We used Kaggle datasets for credit card fraud detection, using pandas to records body for class ==zero for no fraud and sophistication==1 for fraud, matplotlib for plotting the fraud and non fraud facts, train_test_split for information extraction (cut up arrays or matrices into random train and check subsets) and used Logistic Regression device gaining knowledge of set of rules for fraud detection and print predicting rating in line with the set of rules. eventually Confusion matrix changed into plotted on genuine and expected.

In this paper preprocessing is predominant part used sklearn approach is MinMax scalar i.e., facilitates normalize the records. model choice with help of move validation, teach/take a look at split, kfold, GridSearchCV.*Model Selection.*

Model selection is that method of selecting one in every of the models because the final model that addresses the issue. In there we have different steps. They are:

- 1.Data filtering
- 2.Data transformation
- 3.Feature selection
- 4.Feature engineering

For this process we have mainly two methods:

- 1.Probabilistic model selection
- 2.Resampling methods

In this paper we are using resampling methods such as crossvalidation, train/test split, Kflod, GridSearchCV.

4.3 Preprocessing

Records mining methods are utilized in preprocessing for normalize the statistics that is accumulated from kaggle. there is a need to convert because dataset may also have missing values, noisy data. So, we are the usage of records mining technique for cleansing technique [10][12]. before the usage of version choice technique we are used preprocessing approach for lessen the null values then recover the statistics with assist of educate/test break up with assist of MinMaxScaler MinMaxScalar, for every price in each functionMinMaxScalar cipher the minimal price inside the characteristic then divided by using the vary. The range is the distinction among the first most and original minimum. It preserves the shapes of the primary original distribution.

4.4 Feature Engineering

It is the approach of the usage of area statistics to extract alternatives from facts through information processing techniques. these functions are desired to enhance the overall performance of machine studying algorithms. function engineering is notion-about as implemented device studying itself. it is helping for import the models.

```
import NumPy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt import seaborn as sns
```

Gadget getting to know is a subset of AI that trains machines with widespread volumes of information to suppose and act like human beings without being explicitly programmed. in this paper we are using supervised (classification methods) techniques.

Gadget mastering classification models had been used for prediction of android programs. The fashions are available in python open supply software. The short details of every version are defined under.

```
(Loan_ID      0
Gender        13
Married       3
Dependents    15
Education     0
Self_Employed 32
ApplicantIncome 0
CoapplicantIncome 0
LoanAmount    22
Loan_Amount_Term 14
Credit_History 50
Property_Area 0
Loan_Status   0
dtype: int64,
Male         489
Female       112
Name: Gender, dtype: int64,
Yes          398
No           213
Name: Married, dtype: int64,
No           500
Yes           82
Name: Self_Employed, dtype: int64,
1.0          475
0.0           89
Name: Credit_History, dtype: int64)
```

Selection trees

The basic algorithmic rule of name tree desires all attributes or options ought to be discredited. characteristic choice relies on greatest information advantage of alternatives.

The information pictured in name tree will delineate in the sort of IF-THEN rules. This version is companion degree extension of C4.five class algorithms represented through Quinlan.

Random Forest

Random forests are a classifying getting to know framework for characterization (and backslide) that paintings by way of constructing a very big range of decision bushes at making

plans time and yielding the class that's the mode of the classes surrender by using man or woman trees.

Support Vector Machine

Used SVM to build and teach a version put together a show utilizing using n-coordinate plane where n represents the number of features.

SVM creates an hyperplane between datasets that have high acceptance and the datasets which have low acceptance .This creates a pattern recognition approach for the ML system and this creates a faster output generation time .

K-nearest neighbor (KNN)

The KNN algorithm is a simple supervised machine learning algorithm that can be utilized to unravel both classification and replace issues. It is easy to implement and understand but significantly slows as the size of that data on use human mobile records, and classify cells to whether or not the exams are benign (moderate nation) or dangerous (evil kingdom).

Helps vector machines are controlled learning fashions that utilize affiliation R-studying calculation which examine attributes and outstanding design information, applied for utility class. SVM can beneficially carry out a replace using the kernel reverifiable mapping their inputs into excessive dimensional characteristic spaces.

They are designed to hit upon errors in facts at a lower level of element. records validations have been protected within the system in almost every location where there may be a possibility for the user to dedicate errors. The system received accept invalid records. every time invalid facts are keyed in, the system like a shot activates the user and also the consumer ought to over again key in the statistics and additionally the system will be given for the information supplied that the data is accurate. Validations are enclosed anywhere essential.

The device is designed to be a person friendly one. In opportunity words the system has been designed to talk correctly with the person. The gadget has been designed with popup menus.

4.5 Major attributes

Pd.crosstab():

Computes the basic cross organization of two (or more) components. Computes a factor iteration table with the aid of default, unless clusters of values and cumulative operations are exceeded.

Loan_Status	N	Y	All
0.0	82	7	89
1.0	97	378	475
All	179	385	564

Fig. Loan status (N= no , Y=yes)

Need for confusion matrix:

Type (predict class) models have more than one output classes. maximum mistakes measures will tell us the entire error in our version but we cannot use it to find out man or woman times of mistakes in our version. Confusion matrix facilitates us discover the right predictions of a version for exclusive person classes as well as the mistakes the main matrix.

<p>True negative</p> <p>Predicted negative Actual negative</p>	<p>False positive</p> <p>Predicted positive Actual negative</p>
<p>False negative</p> <p>Predicted negative Actual positive</p>	<p>True positive</p> <p>Predicted positive Actual positive</p>

Fig. Confusion Matrix

5. Results

Before mentioning the results in tabular format , let us understand some terms:

•Accuracy: It's worn to discover the part of correctly labeled values. it's far informed us how regularly our classifier is proper. Sum of all actual values divided through total values. quantity of classified samples =TP+TN general wide variety of samples= TP+FP+TN+FN

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + FP + TN + FN)}$$

•Precision: it is used to calculate the fashion's potential to categories high-quality values correct
 variety of categorized values = TP variety of actual values = TP+FP

$$F_1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{recall}} + \frac{1}{\text{precision}}} = 2 \times \frac{\text{precision} \times \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

Bear in mind: To calculate the models potential to predict decent values :

Consider :-

F1- score: It is also referred to as the F score or the F degree. Put any other way, the f1 score conveys the balance between the precision and the bear in mind.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

5.1 Table

After using different algorithms, we have found different accuracies, precision etc.

Data is mentioned below in a tabular format.

Used algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
SVM	83.3	0.84	0.82	0.81

Above table gives us a statistical and comparative overview of different machine learning algorithms which can be efficiently used in bank loan prediction systems.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we proposed customer credit prediction using supervised learning techniques for credit candidates as valid or free customers. In this work, various algorithms were implemented to predict customer credit. Optimal results were obtained with SVM Classifier. With a correct analysis of the pros and cons of the part, we can conclude that this product can be a very efficient part. This application works well and meets all or all of a banker's needs. This part is often simply installed on several different systems. In many cases, computer malfunctions, content errors, and optional key weights are incorporated into machine-controlled predictive systems, so the so-called software systems are safer, more reliable, and more dynamic weight adjustments. can be created in the near future. In the near future, this prediction module can be integrated with the machine-driven processing system module.

The system is trained on old training dataset in futuresoftware can be made such that new testing data should also take part in training data after some fix time.

References

1. Kumar Arun, Garg Ishan, Kaur Sanmeet, — Loan Approval Prediction based on Machine Learning Approach, IOS R Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR - JCE), Vol.18, Issue 3, pp.79 - 81, Veri (May- Jun. 2011)
2. S.Vimala, K. C. Sharmili, —Prediction of Loan Risk using NB and Support Vector Machinel, International Conference on Advancements in Computing Technologies (ICACT 2018), vol. 4, no.2, pp. 110-113, 2018.
3. Pidikiti Supriya, Myneni Pavani, Nagarapu Saisushma, Namburi Vimala Kumari, kVikash, “Loan Prediction by using Machine Learning Models”, International Journal of Engineering and Techniques Volume 5 Issue 2, Mar-Apr 2019.
4. Nikhil Madane, Siddharth Nanda,” Loan Prediction using Decision tree”, Journal of the Gujrat Research History, Volume 21 Issue 14 s, December 2019.
5. Alaraj, M., Abboud, M., “A systematic credit scoring model based on heterogeneous classifier ensembles”, Sep2015.
6. Marc Claesen, Frank De Smet, Johan A. K. Suykens, Bart De Moor, “A Library for Ensemble Learning Using Support Vector Machines”, Jan 2014.
7. Gang Wang, Jian Ma, “Study of corporate credit risk prediction based on Integrating boosting and random subspace”, 2011.
8. T. Zhuyin, and M. Fallahi, “A Prediction Model for Recognition of Bad Credit Customers in Saman Bank Using Neural Networks”, 2011.
9. Kumar Arun,Gaur Ishan,Kaur Sanmit-Loan Prediction based on machine Learning approach,IOSR Journal of computer engineering,,pp.18-21 2016.